

**PERCEPTION AND PRACTICE OF ERGONOMICS IN DENTISTRY
AMONG DENTAL PRACTITIONERS AND POST GRADUATES IN INDIA**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The knowledge pertaining to ergonomics is vital for preventing musculoskeletal disorder. A proper work posture should be inculcated in dental clinical practice to prevent such health hazards.

Materials and Methods: A survey was conducted among the dental postgraduate students for the duration of 3 months. The questionnaire was validated and online Google forms were prepared and circulated among the postgraduate students of various dental institutes. Questionnaire was divided into three parts. Part 1 includes the demographic variables and knowledge towards ergonomics. Part 2 questions are related to awareness toward ergonomics. Part 3 being the practices of ergonomic principles by postgraduates. The resultant responses were recorded in Microsoft Excel format which formed the basic data for the study. The correlation between the source of information related to knowledge and practices about ergonomics was statistically evaluated using the Chi-square test. A P value < 0.05 was measured as statistically significant.

Results: On statistical analysis, there was a statistically significant correlation observed among dental practitioners and dental post graduate students and also amongst the second and the third-year postgraduate students toward basic ergonomics compared to the 1st year.

Conclusion: Comprehensive understanding and awareness regarding the types of ergonomically equipped chairs for practicing in dental clinics among postgraduate was lacking. A proper emphasis on chair side exercise and training should be initiated to prevent any sort of musculoskeletal pains.

Key words: Ergonomics, Musculoskeletal Disorder, Postgraduates, Work posture, Ergonomic Assessment

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INTRODUCTION-

Dental practice requires knowledge and experience of dental procedures with greater precision and accuracy. That necessitates the dental operator's focus, concentration, and patience along with physical and mental resilience. In an ergonomic setting, performing a therapeutic approach and effective practice involve clear working conditions for the dentist and the assistant.

"Ergonomics" is defined as a collection of multidisciplinary knowledge applied to the organization of labor activities and elements that make up work. The key purpose behind the ergonomic principles is to establish a safe, healthy, and comfortable working atmosphere for dental practitioners, thereby preventing health problems which in turn improve productivity.^[1] When ergonomic principles are applied in dentistry, it aims to minimize cognitive and physical distress, prevent occupational diseases related to dental practice, and increase efficiency with enhanced quality and comfort for both the professional and patient.^[2]

Maintaining a proper posture imparts the dentist with more energy to work, reduced stress level, and increased comfort. It is understood that a "good" posture produces more working energy, lowers the stress level, increases comfort, and lowers the risk for

therapeutic errors. A "bad" posture is known to cause fatigue, stress, and a negative attitude to work, high-risk for musculoskeletal disorders, and a poor job quality.^[2]

Musculoskeletal disorders are characterized by the presence of discomfort, and persistent pain in the joints, muscles, tendons, and soft parts, aggravated by repeated movements and prolonged awkward or forced body postures.^[3] Work-related musculoskeletal disorders are one of the primary occupational health risk affecting dentists.^[1] Studies demonstrate that among the wide range of musculoskeletal disorders, back pain is the most common among dentists.^[4] Incorrect working posture can potentially lead to loss of productivity and earning. Therefore, it is essential to install an appropriate working condition and magnification to improve visibility.^[5] Despite the huge risk to the health of dentist, as well dental students, they show unsafe work practices and lack basic ergonomics knowledge.^[6] Good ergonomic practice can prevent the dentist from early retirement.^[1]

Postgraduates undergo a complex educational experience in dental sciences. The residents of the entire specialty are expected to be trained well clinically on patients. All these factors add on to ergonomic circumstances. After a

literature search was performed to find the topics pertaining to knowledge, attitude, and awareness among postgraduate toward ergonomics was at sparse. Hence, the objective of the present study is to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and awareness of postgraduate students toward ergonomics and to compare the practices followed by different postgraduate across various dental institutes inday to day practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study is a cross-sectional questionnaire-based study which was conducted among the dental postgraduate students of various dental colleges across India for the duration of 3 months. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional review board of Peoples Dental College & Hosital ,Bhopal . A total of 452 dental practioners and dental postgraduates made up the sample for the study.

The study objectives were explained and informed consent was obtained from the participants before the questionnaire through online forms. Participants who did not give their consent to participate in the study were excluded from the study. A self-prepared questionnaire was given to the participants in the format of online forms and they were asked to fill the questionnaire as per their convenience.

If any problem arises while filling the questionnaire form, it was immediately solved by the investigator during the period of the study.

The questionnaire consists of 25 closed-ended questions and one open-ended question to evaluate their knowledge, awareness, and attitude toward ergonomics. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, first part contains the demographic details which include gender and professional background. Second part includes a general understanding of ergonomics, application of ergonomics in clinical practice, effective methods and tools in implementing proper ergonomics in clinical practice, and some suggestions related to ergonomics were also invited. The individual responses from each participant were recorded and tabulated on an excel template and subjected to statistical analysis to draw the conclusion from the resultant data.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS-

Data were entered in Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and statistical analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 25.0, (IBM SPSS, Inc. Chicago, Illinois).for statistical analysis Pearson's Chi-squared test was used. A cut off of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant with a 95% confidence interval.

RESULT

A total of 452 participants answered the questionnaire. As mentioned in Table 1, about 148 (61.67%) were female and about 92 (38.33%) were male. The highest number of subjects were from 1st year of MDS 113 (47.08%) followed by 3rd-year 67 (27.92%) and 2nd-year 60 (25.00%).

The distribution of questions and scores related to knowledge are shown in Table 2. While comparing the association between the

gender and knowledge regarding the use of poor fitting gloves used in the dental procedure, there is a statistically significant difference found between them when calculated according to the Chi-square test, as shown in Table 3 ($P = 0.003$).

Subjects when asked questions related to awareness, about 121 (67.22%) female responders believed that emphasis regarding the equipment ergonomics is less in the present dental curriculum and a statistically significant difference was found between the subjects [Table 4] ($P = 0.004$).

Table 1- Demographic distribution of respondent (n-452)

Demographic Variables		n	(%)
Gender	Male	108	23.9
	Female	344	76.1
Working Experience	<1year	236	52.2
	1-4 years	164	36.3
	4-10 years	40	8.8
	>10 Years	12	2.7
Affiliation	Post Graduate	92	20.4
	General Practitioners	300	66.4
	Field Specialist	60	13.3
Total		452	100%

n- Number of respondent

Table 2- Frequency distribution of responses according to perception towards ergonomics in dentistry (n=452)

Perception towards ergonomics	Yes n(%)	No n(%)
Are you acquainted with dental ergonomics	388(85.8%)	64(14.2%)
Do you think practicing dentistry without knowledge of ergonomic principle can lead to musculoskeletal disorders?	428 (94.7%)	24(5.3%)
Is ergonomics equally important for patient as well as dentist	432 (95.6%)	20(4.4%)
Does improper ergonomics can affect the sleep and mental health of dentist	424(93.8%)	28(6.2%)
Are you aware of treatment modalities once you are subjected to musculoskeletal disorders	280 (61.9%)	172(38.1%)

Figure 1- Distribution of experience regarding ergonomics related syndrome

Figure 2- Distribution of most commonly experienced syndrome related to ergonomics

Table 3- Frequency distribution of responses according to practice towards ergonomics in dentistry (n=452)

Practice towards ergonomics	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
Do you perform stretching exercise in between appointments?	280(61.9%)	172(38.1%)
Do you practice under microscope/ loupes for proper accessibility and visibility?	308(68.1%)	144(31.9%)
Have you ever enrolled in any offline/online lectures regarding ergonomics in dentistry?	212(46.9%)	240(53.1%)

Table 4- Distribution of practice towards Dental ergonomics among dental professionals according to gender, working experience and affiliation (n=452)

Practice towards ergonomics		Gender		Affiliation			Working experience			
		Male	Female	Post Graduate	General	Field Specialist	<1 year	1-4 years	5-10 years	>10 years
Do you perform stretching exercise in between appointments?	Yes	80 (17.7%)	228 (50.4%)	60 (13.3%)	216 (47.8%)	32 (7.1%)	184 (40.7%)	100 (22.1%)	20 (4.4%)	4 (0.9%)
	No	28 (6.2%)	116 (25.7%)	32 (7.1%)	84 (18.6%)	28 (6.2%)	52 (11.5%)	64 (14.2%)	20 (4.4%)	8 (2.7%)
p- value		0.129		0.014*			0.000*			
Do you practice under microscope/ loupes for proper accessibility and visibility?	Yes	48 (10.6%)	164 (36.3%)	44 (9.7%)	136 (30.1%)	32 (7.1%)	112 (24.8%)	84 (18.6%)	12 (2.7%)	4 (0.9%)
	No	60 (13.3%)	180 (39.8%)	48 (10.6%)	164 (36.3%)	28 (6.2%)	124 (27.4%)	80 (17.7%)	28 (6.2%)	8 (1.8%)
p- value		0.557		0.516			0.081			

*Statistically significant

DISCUSSION

Maintaining good body postures helps to reduce the energy expenditure, improves function, and protects the individual from an occupational hazard.[7] When applied to dentistry, ergonomics aims reducing the cognitive and physical stress, prevent occupational conditions linked to the practice of dentistry, and increases the performance, with improved quality and superior comfort for both the dental professionals and the patients.

In the recent dental literature, musculoskeletal injuries related terminologies have arisen with an increased frequency. A symptom for musculoskeletal pain includes pain, swelling, tenderness, numbness, and loss of strength. Mechanism of musculoskeletal pain includes prolong static posture of the human body which initiates pain, causes injury, and ceases the workflow. To prevent the occurrence of musculoskeletal injuries, self-contemplation and recognition by the dentists in relation to their own postures, practicing positions, and equipment usage pattern is the first critical step. Such identification will aid in avoiding these risk factors.[8]

In the Indian context, where the number of practicing dentist is increasing, there is a continuous prevalence of musculoskeletal injuries.[4] Ergonomics has always been neglected as a knowledge and attitude point of view, as well it is not the part of dental curriculum in undergraduate as well as postgraduate as proposed by Dental Council of India.[9] As a result, the knowledge of ergonomics is dissipated using informal means only.[4] This necessitates the evaluation of knowledge, awareness, and practices toward ergonomics among postgraduate students during their routine dental procedures.

Therefore, the current cross-sectional questionnaire study was conducted to assess the postgraduates regarding the ergonomic principles and has uncovered interesting and hidden areas of this dynamic field. In our study, we found that about 62.50% of responders were aware of the ergonomic principles.

When noticed, the majority of the respondents (80.83%) applied ergonomics to dentistry as

instruments, equipment, and work posture. This, in general, demonstrates that postgraduate students understand ergonomics as something important, which may benefit their health in the near future.[10] Many postgraduates did recommend that the ergonomic should be supervised by the professors specializing in the area during their clinical activities.

The use of operating stool is complex and is misunderstood among the postgraduates. Dental professionals sit for more than 80–100% of the day in a chair with weak lumbar support and inadequate adjustability, which predisposes them to lower back pain.[11] In our study, about 43.01% of postgraduate were unaware of the saddle and triple-shaped ergonomically designed stool.

Following a correct work posture is fundamental in delivering optimal dental treatment.[12] About 78.75% of respondents in our study had a proper knowledge of the operator's positing while working in maxillary as well as mandibular arch.

In the present study, about 50.42% responders preferred taking microbreaks in between the procedures and which improved their work productivity and about 25% of the responders did practice chairside exercise in between the procedures.

Certain chair side exercise was emphasized by *Shipra Gupta* such as un-twister, trunk rotation, and reversal exercises that can be practiced as microbreaks to improve the working efficiency.[13]

Rhodej et al. emphasized the use of proper size and fit gloves does influence hand comfort.[14] It has been sited that the use of improper gloves does cause carpel tunnel syndrome.[15] The risk factor prevailing this condition is the repetitiveness of work, mechanical stress,

posture, temperature, and vibration.^[16] In this study, when queried, about 79.19% responded that the use of ill-fitting gloves does hinder the treatment procedure.

Long-term maintenance of poor posture can result in chronic muscle pain. Standing involves a different group of muscles, alternating two positions allows one group to rest and the workload is shifted to another group of muscles. Practicing alternative methods between standing and sitting can be an effective tool in reducing fatigability.^[17]

Many of the participants in our study were right-handed. A correct seating position is between 9'o clock to 12'o clock for a right-handed operator, whereas for the left-handed operator, 3'o clock to 12'o clock position is preferred.^[18]

Many responders in our study did agree that working in an incorrect posture can affect in the long run. Hence, a proper postural parameter should be followed. Sitting in an upright symmetrical position, legs slightly apart, and forearms lightly elevated ensures a correct working posture.

In our study, it was found that many of the postgraduates were interested in learning about the recent ergonomic posture through various platforms. Many of them recommended for live demonstrations, workshops, and training to reduce work fatigability. Few responders also mentioned that the ergonomics should be a part of the daily curriculum and should be included as a syllabus in undergraduate as well postgraduate.

Further studies must be conducted among the postgraduate on practical training workshops to prevent the early establishment of postural vices.

CONCLUSION

Four-handed dentistry is an ergonomically efficient way to provide good dental care, leading to an increase in efficiency and productivity of a person in improving the workability toward dental treatment.^[19]

Our study concluded that there is an acceptable level of knowledge and awareness found regarding ergonomics in various dental institutes. The attitude of participants regarding ergonomics is appreciable. Postgraduates should work toward the proper establishment of ergonomic posture in clinics and should influence others too in practicing dentistry in an effortless way.

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